

Decoding the Intricate Roles of Vitamin D in Bone Health: Beyond Calcium Homeostasis

Gupta A^{1*}, Agraval R, Sharma M, Kaur S

Abstract

The intricate relationship between vitamin D and bone health encompasses a diverse spectrum of roles, extending far beyond its classical functions in calcium homeostasis. Apart from the classical role of vitamin D in maintaining calcium homeostasis, it involves intricate intracellular processes that contribute significantly to bone health. This includes modulation of oxidative stress, with vitamin D receptors in osteoblasts and osteoclasts regulating antioxidant enzymes, safeguarding bone cells from oxidative damage. Vitamin D's influence extends to energy metabolism, impacting adipocytes and muscle cells directly. Deficiency is associated with increased adiposity and altered muscle function, emphasizing its regulatory role in adipogenesis, lipolysis, and muscle protein synthesis. This intricate interplay highlights vitamin D's expanded role beyond calcium homeostasis. Vitamin D also emerges as a crucial regulator in promoting the anabolic state of bone. It enhances osteoblast differentiation and mineralization through intricate signalling pathways, ensuring proper bone formation. Simultaneously, it modulates the expression of growth factors and cytokines, promoting bone formation while inhibiting factors associated with bone resorption.

Here we explore the multifaceted impact of vitamin D on bone and its role in preserving skeletal integrity. The review extends to discuss the preventive role of vitamin D in the catabolic state of bone, where bone resorption surpasses formation. Vitamin D's regulatory control over factors such as RANKL and OPG plays a pivotal role in maintaining skeletal integrity, preventing bone loss.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Bone Health, Oxidative Stress, Energy Metabolism, Anabolic State, Catabolic State, Skeletal Integrity

Introduction

Bone health, a crucial determinant of overall well-being, is a complex interplay of various factors, and vitamin D stands out for its indispensable role in preserving skeletal integrity. Traditionally acknowledged for its involvement in calcium and phosphate

homeostasis, vitamin D is essential for maintaining the structural and functional aspects of bone tissue. Recent scientific endeavours have delved deeper into the multifaceted nature of vitamin D's impact on bone, revealing a spectrum of intricate intracellular processes beyond its classical

* Corresponding author. ¹Lohia Institute of Medical Sciences. E-mail addresses: guptaannand72@gmail.com (A. Gupta).

functions. This comprehensive review aims to elucidate the evolving understanding of vitamin D in bone health, shedding light on its newfound roles in modulating intracellular mechanisms critical for the maintenance and regulation of bone homeostasis.

The classic role of vitamin D in calcium homeostasis is well-established, as it facilitates intestinal absorption, renal reabsorption, and mobilization of calcium from bone, ensuring the optimal mineralization of the skeletal matrix (Lips et al., 2006). However, recent studies have expanded our comprehension by uncovering its involvement in intricate intracellular processes that intricately contribute to bone health. This includes the modulation of oxidative stress, where vitamin D receptors in osteoblasts and osteoclasts contribute to the regulation of antioxidant enzymes, exerting a protective effect against oxidative damage and preserving bone mass (Sassi et al., 2018.). Moreover, vitamin D's influence extends to energy metabolism, with its receptors present in adipocytes and muscle cells, suggesting a direct impact on adipogenesis, lipolysis, and muscle protein synthesis, all of which are integral components of the intricate relationship between energy metabolism and bone health (Bischoff-Ferrari, et al. 2018).

Oxidative Stress and Vitamin D

Oxidative stress, a state characterized by an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and the antioxidant defence system, has emerged as a pivotal factor in the pathogenesis of various bone disorders. This phenomenon is marked by an excessive generation of ROS, leading to cellular damage and disruption of normal physiological processes in bone tissue (Manolagas et al., 2010). In this intricate landscape, vitamin D has been identified as a key player in the maintenance of bone health through its ability to counteract oxidative stress.

Vitamin D, operating through its receptors located in osteoblasts and osteoclasts, showcases a remarkable capacity to mitigate oxidative stress within the bone microenvironment. Studies have demonstrated that vitamin D enhances the activity of antioxidant enzymes, such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase, crucial components of the cellular defence against ROS-induced damage (Tamer & Mesci, 2018.). Furthermore, vitamin D exerts a direct influence on reducing ROS levels, thus contributing to the restoration of redox homeostasis in bone cells. This antioxidative property of vitamin D plays a pivotal role in protecting osteoblasts and osteoclasts from oxidative damage, ultimately preserving bone mass and integrity in the face of heightened oxidative stress conditions (Gao & Wang, 2019).

As a result, the interplay between vitamin D and oxidative stress not only highlights the importance of vitamin D beyond its traditional roles but also underscores its potential therapeutic implications in managing oxidative stress-related bone disorders. The elucidation of these intricate cellular mechanisms provides a foundation for the development of targeted interventions aimed at preserving bone health in conditions characterized by elevated oxidative stress.

Energy Metabolism and Vitamin D

The intricate link between energy metabolism and bone health has become increasingly evident, with vitamin D emerging as a pivotal player in this complex interplay. Vitamin D receptors expressed in adipocytes and muscle cells suggest a direct regulatory influence on key components of energy metabolism. Studies have illuminated the significance of vitamin D in maintaining the delicate balance between energy homeostasis and bone health, shedding light on the consequences of vitamin D deficiency on both adipose and muscle tissues (Vimalaswaran et al., 2013).

Vitamin D deficiency has been linked to increased adiposity, as evidenced by studies highlighting a positive correlation between low vitamin D levels and higher adipose tissue accumulation. This association underscores the importance of vitamin D in regulating adipogenesis, the process by which precursor cells differentiate into mature adipocytes, influencing overall adipose tissue composition (Wortsman et al., 2000). Concurrently, altered muscle function is observed in individuals with vitamin D deficiency, further complicating the intricate relationship between energy metabolism and bone health. Vitamin D's regulatory role extends to influencing muscle protein synthesis, a critical process for maintaining muscle mass and function, thus contributing to the overall musculoskeletal health (Bischoff-Ferrari et al., 2009).

The regulation of energy metabolism by vitamin D involves intricate signalling pathways, encompassing adipogenesis, lipolysis, and muscle protein synthesis. These pathways collectively contribute to the maintenance of optimal energy balance, ensuring the preservation of bone health. Understanding the multifaceted role of vitamin D in energy metabolism not only expands our knowledge of its functions beyond calcium homeostasis but also opens avenues for targeted interventions aimed at optimizing both metabolic and skeletal well-being.

Anabolic State of Bone and Vitamin D

Vitamin D emerges as a crucial regulator in promoting the anabolic state of bone, orchestrating a complex network of cellular processes that facilitate bone formation. Its involvement extends beyond the traditional roles of calcium homeostasis, as vitamin D plays a pivotal role in enhancing the differentiation and mineralization of osteoblasts, the primary cells responsible for bone formation (Pike & Christakos, 2017). This regulatory influence is executed through a myriad of signalling pathways that coordinate

the intricate dance of molecular events essential for optimal bone health.

The differentiation of osteoblasts into mature, mineralizing cells is a pivotal step in bone formation, and vitamin D plays a central role in this process. Through its receptors in osteoblasts, vitamin D orchestrates gene expression patterns that promote the differentiation of precursor cells into fully functional osteoblasts (Fleet & DeSmet, 2018). Furthermore, vitamin D's impact on bone extends to the regulation of mineralization, ensuring the proper deposition of calcium and phosphate in the extracellular matrix, a critical aspect of bone formation and maintenance.

Beyond its direct influence on osteoblasts, vitamin D exerts regulatory control over the expression of growth factors and cytokines that contribute to bone formation. This includes the upregulation of bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs) and insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), both essential for stimulating osteoblast activity and bone matrix synthesis (Norman et al., 2002). Simultaneously, vitamin D inhibits factors associated with bone resorption, such as receptor activator of nuclear factor-kappaB ligand (RANKL), thereby tipping the balance in favour of bone formation over resorption.

Catabolic State of Bone and Vitamin D

The intricate interplay between vitamin D and bone health extends to the prevention of the catabolic state, where bone resorption surpasses bone formation, leading to a loss of bone mass. Vitamin D exerts regulatory control over factors associated with bone resorption, contributing to the maintenance of skeletal integrity. Its involvement in preventing the catabolic state involves complex interactions at the cellular and molecular levels, emphasizing the multifaceted nature of vitamin D's impact on bone health.

Vitamin D, through its receptors in osteoblasts and osteoclasts, plays a crucial role in modulating the expression of receptor activator

of nuclear factor-kappa B ligand (RANKL), a key mediator of osteoclast differentiation and activity (Takahashi et al., 2018). Through inhibiting RANKL expression, vitamin D reduces the activation of osteoclasts, the cells responsible for bone resorption. Additionally, vitamin D enhances the expression of osteoprotegerin (OPG), a decoy receptor that competes with RANKL for binding to its receptor, thereby further attenuating osteoclast activity (Zhang et al., 2002).

Furthermore, vitamin D is implicated in inhibiting the production of proinflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin-6 (IL-6) and tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), which play a role in promoting bone resorption (Rahman et al., 2007). This way, through dampening the inflammatory milieu, vitamin D contributes to the attenuation of bone resorption processes, maintaining a balance between bone formation and resorption.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this comprehensive review synthesizes a wealth of scientific evidence to underscore the intricate and multifaceted impact of vitamin D on bone health. Traditionally acknowledged for its canonical role in calcium homeostasis, vitamin D has revealed a complex repertoire of functions that extend beyond the regulation of mineralization. Recent research highlights its involvement in intricate intracellular processes, including the modulation of oxidative stress, wherein vitamin D's receptors in osteoblasts and osteoclasts contribute significantly to the regulation of antioxidant enzymes. This antioxidative property emerges as a crucial facet of vitamin D's role, safeguarding bone cells from oxidative damage and preserving overall bone mass and integrity. The understanding of these nuanced cellular mechanisms provides a foundation for targeted interventions in conditions associated with heightened oxidative stress and underscores the therapeutic potential of vitamin

D in managing oxidative stress-related bone disorders.

Moreover, the exploration of vitamin D's influence on energy metabolism unravels its direct regulatory impact on adipocytes and muscle cells. Deficiency of vitamin D is linked to increased adiposity and altered muscle function, emphasizing its integral role in adipogenesis, lipolysis, and muscle protein synthesis. The intricate signalling pathways involved in the regulation of energy metabolism not only expand our comprehension of vitamin D's functions but also open avenues for interventions aimed at optimizing both metabolic and skeletal well-being. The comprehensive overview of vitamin D's roles in promoting the anabolic state of bone further solidifies its significance in bone health. Through the enhancement of osteoblast differentiation, mineralization, and the modulation of growth factors, vitamin D contributes crucially to bone formation, emphasizing its potential therapeutic implications in optimizing skeletal integrity.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.